

PLANT DISEASE DETECTION USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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Abstract— The secret of preventing losses in the production and quantity of agricultural products is the identification of plant diseases. The research on plant diseases refers to examinations of patterns of the plant that may be observed with the naked eye. The manual monitoring of plant diseases is highly challenging. It necessitates a significant amount of work, knowledge of plant diseases, and also excessive procedure duration. As a result, image processing is employed to detect plant disease by taking photos of the leaves and comparing them to data sets. The data set consist of different plant in the image format. Apart from detection users are recommended with the cure fertilizers CNN algorithm is used for the plant disease model training.

Keywords- Plant disease, deep learning, CNN, Tensor flow, Classification, PIL.

INTRODUCTION

India is a developed nation where agriculture supports around 70% of the population. Farmers can choose from a wide variety of acceptable crops thanks to their locating plant-safe insecticides. Therefore, crop damage would result in a significant loss in productivity, which would have an impact on the economy.

The most vulnerable component of plants, the leaves, is where disease symptoms first appear. From the very beginning of the growing process, the crops must be checked for illnesses. from the beginning of their life cycle till they may be harvested. Initially, experts had to manually check the crop fields using the time-consuming, traditional naked-eye observation approach to keep a watch on the plants for illnesses. A variety of strategies have been used in recent years to produce automatic and semi-automatic plant disease detection systems, and automatic disease detection by simply observing the symptoms on the plant leaves makes it both simpler and more affordable. These methods have so far shown to be quicker, less expensive, and more precise than the farmers' manual observation method. There

are many instances where farmers lack comprehensive understanding of the crops and the diseases that can impact them. Instead of going to an expert and seeking their guidance, farmers can use this document efficiently to increase productivity

A machine learning algorithm is used to assess the leaf, determine whether it is defective or not, and, if it is, identify The disease and recommend remedies. The topic of our paper is spotting diseases in leaves. Using CNN, we developed our model. It uses a common deep-learning model. In the event of disease detection, this technique can extract features from the source image. Because of its end-to-end structure

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mr.V Suresh, D Gopinath, M Hemavarthini, K Jayanthan, Mohana Krishnan,[1] in their paper titled “Plant Disease Detection using Image Processing” detect the plant disease. This paper focuses on accurately identifying plants with diseases and healthy plants, and it accomplishes this task by using numerous photos of plant diseases. This study employs an Android app to find plant illnesses. It uses a convolutional neural network and algorithms to identify species and illnesses in crop leaves.

Pooja V, Rahul Das, Kanchana[2] in their paper titled “Identification of Plant Leaf Diseases using Image Processing Techniques” focuses on the detection of plant diseases using several methodologies, including support vector machines (SVM). The image's recognition rate is determined. The disease is identified after the image has been segmented using the K-means clustering technique.

Samhitha Suda, Dr. C N Sujatha[3] in their paper titled “Leaf Disease Detection and Classification” In this paper, a novel approach to plant disease recognition using convolutional neural networks, focusing on the classification of leaf images. The model system receives an image of a leaf with maize disease. It then undergoes picture acquisition, creating a

digitally encoded representation of the image. After that, this image is pre-processed, or turned into an intensity image. A data matrix called an intensity picture represents intensities within a range. The suggested method, which is based on Python, has a detection accuracy of about 98 percent for each ailment. Using Google's GPU for processing can improve precision and speed.

II. METHODOLOGY

The objective of the project is to identify the leaf disease by uploading a leaf that has been infected with a disease, the system was put into place, and the disease was identified along with cure recommendation. The classification of plant diseases in the paper is done using a Flask server and a trained deep-learning model.

The algorithm used for the plant disease detection is

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):

For the diagnosis of plant diseases, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have become a potent deep learning technique. Recent research has shown that CNNs are effective at correctly identifying and categorizing plant diseases from photographs of leaves, stems, and other plant parts. There are a number of processes required in developing a CNN-based plant disease detection system. These consist of:

Data Gathering: Photographs of diseased plants must be taken and labelled with the appropriate disease classification. Images of damaged plants must be taken using a high-resolution camera in order to collect data. The photos must next be assigned to the appropriate disease groups, which calls for an in-depth understanding of plant pathology. The data should be representative of the target population and cover a wide range of plant species and disease types.

Data Preprocessing: In order to reduce noise, normalize image size, and improve contrast, the photos need to be preprocessed. In order to create a system that can reliably and accurately identify plant diseases using deep learning techniques such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), data preparation is a crucial step. The fundamental objective of data preparation is to enhance the input data's quality and suitability for the CNN model to learn useful features.

Model Training: The model is then trained using preprocessed images. Using labelled data, the model is trained on photos of either healthy or ill plants. The images are fed through the CNN architecture during training, and model parameters are updated to reduce the discrepancy between expected and real labels. To train the model to correctly categorise photographs, the labelled data, which comprises of pictures of healthy or ill plants, is employed. The model gains the ability to recognise patterns and characteristics in the photos that distinguish healthy plants from unhealthy ones throughout training.

Model Validation: After the model has been trained, it is tested using a different dataset of fresh photos. This stage makes that the model is robust to generalisation and isn't overfitting the training set of data.

TensorFlow:

A popular machine learning framework called TensorFlow is frequently used to create the deep learning model, for detecting plant diseases. TensorFlow offers a wide range of tools and features that make it suitable for creating CNN models for detecting plant diseases. The image data can be preprocessed with TensorFlow using tools for image augmentation, including rotation, flipping, and zooming. These methods can aid in growing the training dataset's size and variety, which will boost the model's accuracy. Additionally, TensorFlow offers a selection of pre-trained CNN models that have been trained on sizable datasets like ImageNet, including VGG16, ResNet, and Inception. These pre-trained models can serve as a foundation for the creation of plant disease detection models, and they can be improved upon using smaller plant disease datasets. The Keras API, a high-level interface that enables quick prototyping of CNN models, is one of the APIs offered by TensorFlow for creating and training CNN models. Convolutional, pooling, and dense pre-built layers, among others, are available in the Keras API and may be quickly combined to create a CNN model for detecting plant diseases. TensorFlow offers a complete set of tools and functionalities for creating CNN models for detecting plant diseases. For academics and developers building plant disease detection models, it is a popular option due to its simplicity of use, adaptability, and thorough documentation.

PIL package

The image data is preprocessed using the PIL package before being fed into the CNN model. To open and resize the input image specifically to the size required by the CNN model, use the PIL package. The request to the Flask server includes the input image as a base64-encoded string. The image data is then turned into a PIL image object using the BytesIO class from the io module after being decoded using `base64.b64decode()`. The PIL picture is then resized using the `resize()` method to a fixed size of (224, 224). This size matches the CNN model's input size, which is what the plant disease detection code uses. Additionally, the image is transformed into a numpy array and normalised by dividing by 255.0 to guarantee that pixel values lie between 0 and 1. Following the preprocessing stage, the numpy array used to represent the image is fed into the loaded CNN model to determine whether plant disease is present in the image. In general, the PIL package is crucial to the preprocessing stage of the code for detecting plant diseases since it lets the input image to be correctly formatted and enlarged before being fed into the CNN model.

III. RESULT

Based on the dataset provided the plant disease can be identified and a small description of what the disease is provided and the cure is recommended. We can determine the plant disease by uploading the image of the disease affected plant leaf. First we have to upload the image of the

leaf which is affected by the disease and press the predict button as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1

When the predict button is clicked the input image will be checked with the trained data and if there is any matching and the most matching profile will be printed as the output as shown in figure 2

Figure 2

The cure fertilizers are also recommended with the disease as shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3

IV. CONCLUSION

The paper provides a method to detect plant leaf disease using Convolutional Neural Network. Here primarily we teach the

system various common diseases that may occur to the leaf. The dataset contains various class of diseases. When the input image is uploaded the image is compared with the dataset and the most accurate result will be provided. The most matching result will be considered as the output disease with a short description remedies and cure fertilizers. The system is very helpful for automated disease detection.

V. REFERENCE

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